

ON THE NONLINEAR THERMOVISCOELASTIC CREEP BEHAVIOR OF FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Based on Schapery's approach for nonlinear viscoelasticity a characterization method was developed, to evaluate the creep compliance transverse to the fiber direction $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and the shear compliance $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$ of the single lamina of continuous fiber-reinforced composite materials. This method serves to determine the nonlinearity of the creep response from creep experiments having a short loading duration (10 hours). The long-term behavior and the influence of temperature are characterized by means of the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP), applying results of creep experiments and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). This method reduced the time and experimental efforts to describe the creep behavior of a carbon-fiber-reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and epoxy resin significantly.

INTRODUCTION

Using polymer matrix composites as the material for structural applications, an important issue is the influence of the viscoelastic nature of the polymer matrix on the long-term behavior of the construction. While the glass or carbon-fiber reinforcement can be considered as elastic, the polymer matrix exhibits viscoelastic behavior. Therefore viscoelastic phenomena are found with composite materials, particularly when subjected to high thermal and mechanical loading [1]. The viscoelastic behavior results in different phenomena, i.e. creep.

The aim of the present investigation is to characterize of the nonlinear thermoviscoelastic creep behavior of the single lamina of continuous fiber-reinforced composite materials usually used for structural components. The creep behavior of multidirectional reinforced laminates can be predicted based on the characterization of the single lamina, to assess the long-term behavior of structural components [1,2].

THEORETICAL APPROACH

Accordingly to the most frequent used notation, the 1-2 coordinates describe the local orientation of a unidirectional reinforced lamina, where 1 coincides with the fiber direction.

For a single ply having orthotropic material properties, the compliance matrix [J] contains four principal compliances to describe plane stress situations. The fiber-dominated compliances J_{11} and J_{12} can be considered as thermoelastic for continuous fiber-reinforced composites. In order to characterize the nonlinear thermoviscoelastic behavior of a single lamina, it is necessary to determine the creep compliance transverse to the fiber direction $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and the shear compliance $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$.

Schapery's constitutive Eqn of the characterization of a nonlinear viscoelastic material under uniaxial loading and isothermal conditions can be written as [3,4]:

$$\epsilon = g_0 J_0 \sigma + g_1 \int_0^t \Delta J (\psi - \psi') \frac{\partial g_2 \sigma}{\partial \tau} d\tau \tag{1}$$

J_0 and ΔJ are the initial and the transient components of the linear viscoelastic creep compliance, respectively. ψ and ψ' are reduced times defined as:

$$\psi = \int_0^\tau \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma} \qquad \psi' = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma} \tag{2}$$

g_0, g_1, g_2 and a_σ are stress-dependent factors describing the nonlinearity of the material response. In the linear viscoelastic range, where $g_0 = g_1 = g_2 = 1$, Eqn (1) is reduced to Boltzmann's superposition integral.

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION METHOD

Based on Schapery's approach, a characterization method was developed to evaluate $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$.

It has been shown that excellent modeling of the creep response of polymers both with and without reinforcement is achieved through the assumption $a_\sigma = 1$ [1,5,6]. Instead of a_σ , the shift factor a_T and the reduced time ξ were added to Eqn 1 to describe temperature dependence:

$$\xi = \int_0^\tau \frac{dt'}{a_T}; \qquad \xi' = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_T} \tag{3}$$

The time dependence of the linear creep compliance can be approximated by a Prony-Dirichlet series:

$$J(t) = J_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m J_i [1 - \exp(-t / \tau_i)] \tag{4}$$

For the stress history of a creep experiment, $\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 H(t)$ (σ_0 = creep stress and $H(t)$ = Heaviside's unit step function), and with $g_t = g_1 g_2$ Eqn 1 results in:

$$J(T, t, \sigma) = g_0 J_0 + g_t \sum_{i=1}^m J_i [1 - \exp(-t / \tau_i)], \quad (5)$$

where

$$g_0 = (T, \sigma); \quad g_t = (T, \sigma); \quad a_T = (T) \quad (6)$$

Eqn 5 describes the nonlinear thermoviscoelastic creep behavior of thermorheological simple materials, where g_0 describes the nonlinearity of the instantaneous response and g_t characterizes the nonlinearity of the transient creep response.

The experimental procedure to determine the material parameters is shown in Fig. 1. Since the nonlinearity factors of a material exhibit no time dependence, they can be determined from creep experiments having a short loading duration [5,6]. A numerical procedure based on the least-squares technique is applied to evaluate the nonlinearity factors from creep experiments performed at different stress levels and temperatures.

The temperature and long-term behavior of the viscoelastic response can be characterized by means of the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). In addition to the creep experiments, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) is performed to better characterize the influence of temperature on the viscoelastic behavior. As for the creep experiment, the specimen should be tension-loaded during the DMA. The maximum load applied should be chosen within the range of linear viscoelasticity. To evaluate the creep compliance $J(T, t)$ from the results of the DMA (storage and loss compliance $J'(T, \omega)$ and $J''(T, \omega)$), a semiempirical transformation procedure is applied [7].

EXPERIMENTAL

The investigation was performed on a thermoset and on a thermoplastic matrix composite material. Both materials are supplied in the form of unidirectional reinforced prepreg tapes having a nominal fiber volume content of 60%. The epoxy resin matrix composite was Fibredux 6376C (Ciba-Geigy AG) reinforced with T800 carbon fibers (Toray Industries, Inc.). The matrix of the prepreg material is a toughened epoxy resin with a glass transition temperature of about 180°C. The thermoplastic system used was the APC-2 material (ICI). The semicrystalline PEEK matrix of the system with a glass transition temperature of about 145°C was reinforced with IM6 carbon fibers (Hercules, Inc.). Laminate $[90_4]_{sym}$ was used to characterize $J_{22}(T, t, \sigma)$ and the laminate $[\pm 45_4]_{sym}$ to characterize $J_{66}(T, t, \sigma)$. In addition, the corresponding neat resins were investigated.

The creep-testing facility consists of several stations (lever loading system), each equipped with strain and force measuring units. Tests at elevated temperatures have been conducted inside thermostatically controlled chambers. The creep experiments were performed at stress levels ranging from 10 to 90% of the ultimate tensile load up to a temperature of 140°C.

Using the dynamic mechanical analyzer (Eplexor from Gabo Qualimeter Inc.), the response of a material is measured to sinusoidal stress by characterizing the temperature and frequency dependence of the storage modulus and the loss modulus. The temperature range from 20 to 200°C was investigated for the thermoplastic material. A maximum temperature of 250°C was selected for the thermoset material. The temperature range was swept in steps of 5°C. At each step the temperature was kept constant in the test chamber and the material response was determined for 7 frequencies (0.1/0.22/0.46/1/2.15/4.64/10 Hz).

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the characterization method.

RESULTS

The use of the characterization method is shown exemplarily for $J_{22}(T, t, \sigma)$ of the carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK.

Fig. 2 shows one series of short-term creep tests of laminate $[90_4]_{\text{sym}}$ at a test temperature of 80°C. These short-term curves, along with the others at different temperatures (23, 100 and 120°C) that are not shown, were used to evaluate the stress and temperature dependence of the nonlinearity factors $g_{022}(T, \sigma)$ and $g_{t22}(T, \sigma)$ (Fig. 3). $g_{022}(T, \sigma)$ and $g_{t22}(T, \sigma)$ are given as a function of the applied creep stress σ_2 .

It was found that the nonlinear viscoelastic behavior of $J_{22}(T, t, \sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T, t, \sigma)$ for both materials is different. Since for $J_{22}(T, t, \sigma)$ the influence of temperature on the stress level resulting in nonlinear behavior is small, $J_{22}(T, t, \sigma)$ exhibits linear viscoelastic behavior for a large temperature and loading range (up to 120°C and 60% of the ultimate load). On the other hand, the shear compliance exhibits nonlinear thermoviscoelastic behavior. While at 23°C the shear compliance $J_{66}(T, t, \sigma)$ of both materials exhibits nonlinear behavior at stress levels higher than 25 MPa, this range is shifted to 8 MPa at a temperature of 120°C.

Furthermore the creep experiments showed that the instantaneous response of the compliances $J_{22}(T, t, \sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T, t, \sigma)$ is almost linear. The influence of temperature on the nonlinear instantaneous response is less sensitive than on the nonlinear transient response.

Figure 2: Creep experiments of carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK, Laminate [90₄]sym, 80°C.

The temperature and frequency dependence of $J'_{22}(T, \omega)$ of the thermoplastic matrix composite material determined by DMA is shown in Fig. 4. The maximum load applied was 5 MPa, within the range of linear viscoelasticity, as can be seen in Fig. 3.

Vertical shifting only was applied for both materials to construct the master curves for the results of the creep experiments and of the DMA. Fig. 5 shows the master curves for J_{22} of the thermoplastic matrix composite material (reference temperature $T_0 = 20^\circ\text{C}$). The master curves resulting from the creep experiments and from the dynamic mechanical analysis describe a similar time dependence of J_{22} .

Figure 3: Nonlinearity factors for the carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK, Laminate [90₄]sym.

Figure 4: Storage compliance J'_{22} of carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK, Laminate $[90_4]_{sym}$.

The segments of the curves of the DMA overlap by more than 70%, whereas the curve segments of the creep experiments partly overlap by less than 10%. Therefore the characterization of the thermoviscoelastic behavior could be improved significantly by the DMA, being less time and cost-consuming than additional creep experiments.

Figure 5: Master curves for carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK, Laminate $[90_4]_{sym}$.

Figure 6: Shift factors a_{Tm} , a_{T22} and a_{T66} for the thermoplastic material.

The shift factors determined for the thermoplastic material are shown in Fig. 6. Good agreement can be found between the shift factors determined from the creep experiments and from the DMA. For both materials, the shift factors a_{T22} and a_{T66} for the compliances $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$ exhibit a similar temperature dependence. In the case of the thermoplastic material, significant differences between the shift factors a_{Tm} of the neat PEEK and of the fiber-reinforced PEEK were found.

Figure 7: Predicted long-term creep behavior of the carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK, Laminate $[90_4]_{sym}$, $80^\circ C$.

The long-term creep behavior of the materials could be predicted (Fig. 7) using Eqn 3. A comparison between experiment and prediction was performed for the time frame accessible for the experiment. The error between experiment and modeling is less than 5% for strain levels up to 0.9%. Higher errors of about 20% appeared at strain levels below 1%. This was caused by micro-damage to the material and by the relaxation of residual thermal stresses. It has to be noted that aging effects or material damage, influencing the long-term behavior, are not covered by the model.

Comparing both materials shows that the influence of temperature on the creep behavior is greater for the thermoplastic matrix material. However, the viscoelastic response of both materials is comparable up to a temperature of 80°C.

SUMMARY

The characterization method developed to describe the nonlinear thermoviscoelastic creep behavior was applied successfully for a carbon-fiber-reinforced PEEK and epoxy resin. Applying this procedure meant that the time and experimental effort for describing the creep compliances $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$ could be reduced significantly.

It was found that the viscoelastic behavior of the compliances $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$ is different for both materials. While even at high temperatures (120°C) the creep compliance $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ exhibits linear viscoelastic behavior for a large loading range (up to 60% of the ultimate load), the shear compliance $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$ exhibits nonlinear thermoviscoelastic behavior.

The TTSP revealed that the shift factors a_{T22} and a_{T66} for the compliances $J_{22}(T,t,\sigma)$ and $J_{66}(T,t,\sigma)$ exhibit a similar temperature dependence. On the other hand great differences can appear between the shift factors of the neat and that of the reinforced resin.

The long-term creep behavior of the laminates $[90_4]_{\text{sym}}$ and $[\pm 45_4]_{\text{sym}}$ could be predicted with an error of about 5% for strain levels below 0.9%.

Comparing both materials indicates that the influence of temperature on the creep behavior is greater for the thermoplastic matrix material. However, the viscoelastic response of both materials is comparable up to a temperature of 80°C.

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